

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE FRUITS OF *SOLANUM NIGRUM*, LINN PART I. THE COMPOSITION OF THE OIL FROM THE SEEDS.

BY G. P. PENDSE.

Solanum nigrum (N. O. *Solanaceae*), known in Hindustani as *Gurkamai* and *Chhoti Makoi*, is widely cultivated in India. The description of the plant and its medicinal properties are given in detail by Dymock ("*Pharmacographica Indica*," 1891, II, 549) and Basu and Kirtikar ("*Indian Medicinal Plants*," 1918, II, 889). The berries of the plant are of great importance in Hindu medicine as being useful as a tonic, and in heart diseases, in fevers, diarrhoea, eye diseases, chronic enlargement of the liver and various other ailments.

Genevil and Desforges (*cf.* Dymock, *loc. cit.*) isolated the active principle of these fruits and assigned to it the formula $C_{45}H_7O_{16}N$ and named it as solanine. The present paper deals with an account of the fixed oil obtained from the seeds of the fruits. The juice, the husk and the oil-free seeds are under investigation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

20 Kg. of the fresh fruits yielded: juice, 6 litres (30%); husk (dried), 0.75 kg. (3.75%); seeds, 1.9 kg. (9.5%).

The powdered seeds (1.9 kg.) on exhaustive extraction with petroleum ether (b.p. 56-60°) yielded about 380 g. (about 2%) of a greenish-yellow oil having characteristic odour of the drug. The crude oil was purified in the usual way with animal charcoal and Fullers' earth. The oil is free from nitrogen and sulphur and has been found to belong to the Drying class of oils. The physical and chemical constants are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

n_D^{25} (in alcoholic solution),	-6.61	Sapon. value	184.7
Sp. gravity	0.8964 at 30°	Acetyl value	9.97
Viscosity	7.12 (compared to rape oil)	Hehner's value	93.10
Ref. index	1.4436 at 30°	Iodine value	111.7
Solidifying pt.	-7°	Unsaponifiable	
Acid value	2.4	matter	1.4-1.6%

150 G. of the oil were saponified with alcoholic potash and the unsaponifiable matter extracted with ether. The fatty acids were liberated and purified in the usual way. Table II gives the constants of the mixed fatty acids.

TABLE II.

Consistency.	Liquid.	Neutralisation value	183.4
Sp. gravity	0.8682 at 30°	Mean M. W.	305.2
Ref. index	1.4125 at 30°	Iodine value	112.4

The mixture of the fatty acids was then separated into the saturated and unsaturated acids by Twitchell's method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, **13**, 806). During the separation a small quantity of resinous mass insoluble in ether was separated. Table III gives the percentage, mean M. W. and iodine values of the saturated and unsaturated acids.

TABLE III.

Acids.	% in the mixed acids.	% in the oil.	Iodine value	Mean M.W.
Saturated	5.88	5.48	3.61	280.4
Unsaturated	94.12	87.62	114.8	276.6

Examination of the Unsaturated Acids.

The unsaturated acids were systematically analysed qualitatively by oxidation with potassium permanganate. Hexahydroxystearic acid could not be detected in the oxidation products showing thereby the absence of linolenic acid. Ether extracted a crystalline acid (m.p. 134-36°) which was identified as dihydroxystearic acid. The ether insoluble portion on extraction with boiling water yielded an acid (m.p. 170-72°), which was proved to be tetrahydroxystearic acid. The formation of these two acids and the absence of hexahydroxystearic acid prove the presence of linolic and oleic acids and the absence of linolenic acid in the unsaturated acids.

The quantitative estimation of the acids was done by the bromine addition products by the method of Jamieson and Baughmann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1197). Table IV gives the results of the analysis of the bromine addition products.

WEIGHTING OF INDIAN SILK.

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Weber (*Textilber.*, 1936, 17, 147) has made a detailed study of the tin weighting process on silk fibres and considers that stannic phosphate formed as a result of the action of the unhydrolysed stannic chloride and the di-sodium phosphate of the fixing bath has got a detrimental effect on the fibres. Attempts have been made to substitute tin with other heavy metals like zinc (Berg and Imhoff, U.S.P., 1926, 1579628) and lead (Berg, Imhoff and Heiberg, U.S.P., 1935, 1990449, and 1990450). But in these patents a treatment with tin as a preliminary to the process is considered necessary. However, a more recent patent (Rotheli, U.S.P., 1935, 2010324), in weighting with lead under certain experimental conditions covered by the patent, completely avoids the use of tin. It is claimed that a weighting of 200% is obtained without adversely affecting the tensile strength of the fibres.

In India silks are not generally weighted before selling but the bulk of them are sold in a raw state (private communication from the sericultural expert, Madras). The following paper describes the results of a detailed study of the conditions of the weighting of Indian silk with lead acetate directly. Two varieties of silk locally known as *Eri*-silk and the Mysore-Japanese cross were chosen for the study.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Weighting Procedure.—Exactly weighted quantities of silk (usually 0.5 g.) were kept immersed in 50 c.c. of the weighting solution for a definite time. Then the fibres were thoroughly washed with large amounts of water and were dried at 78° in an air oven for one hour. The increase in weight noted and the percentage weighting calculated. The fibres before weighting were also kept in the drying chamber and it was assumed that the humidity of atmosphere did not vary appreciably during the days the experiments were conducted. The density of the weighting solution was noted by means of Westphal balance.

Breaking Strength.—Instead of measuring the tensile strength as such, the weight necessary to break a definite length of the fibre under free suspension was noted. Six inches of fibre were suspended by corks

TABLE VI.

Fraction.	B p.	Wt. of the fraction.	Sapon value.	Mean M. W.	Acids		M.p. of liberated acids.
					Palmi- tic	Stearic	
1	170°-185°/1 mm.	2.64 g.	202.4	277.2	1.90 g. (71.56%)	0.62 g. (23.4%)	63-65°
2	185-200°/0.7 mm.	1.52	196.6	285.4	0.68 g. (43.87%)	0.80 g. (51.21%)	64-66°
3	Residue	3.84	190.8	294.1	0.52 g. (14.5%)	3.12 g. (80.71%)	67-68°

Examination of the Unsaponifiable Matter.

The unsaponifiable matter (1.5%), obtained from the soap solution by means of ether, was washed in ethereal solution with water. The dried ethereal solution was next distilled when white silky flakes were obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol as colourless silky flakes, m.p. 127—29°. The acetyl derivative was prepared in the usual manner, m.p. 119—20°. The optical rotation in alcoholic solution was $(\alpha)_D^{25} = -30.5^\circ$. The unsaponifiable matter gave the colour reactions of a phytosterol.

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